

Analyzing Product Reviews to understand Customer Sentiment: A Machine Learning Approach

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Abstract— Sentiment analysis is a popular technique used to determine the sentiment expressed in a piece of text, such as a product review. In this project, we explore the effectiveness of the TextBlob library for conducting sentiment analysis on a dataset of product reviews. We extract text data from the reviews and use TextBlob to calculate the sentiment polarity score, which ranges from -1 to 1, indicating negative, neutral, or positive sentiment expressed in the text. The results are then visualized using a graph to identify the products with the most positive or negative sentiment.

Keywords –Naïve Bayes, sentiment analysis, TextBlob.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis is a crucial aspect of text mining, which involves analyzing a dataset of varying opinions expressed by different users in a specific category. This analysis is commonly performed using machine learning techniques, which facilitate effective text classification. With the rise of online shopping, understanding the opinions of existing users has become increasingly essential for making informed decisions. Sentiment analysis can help users make better choices by analyzing the reviews and identifying predominant emotions, such as sadness, anger, or happiness.

Texts are classified into two primary categories, positive and negative, and the category with the highest prevalence is declared to be the category of the text or sentence. The analysis can be performed for an entire document, a single sentence, or a single word. Many tools and classification techniques are available to perform effective sentiment analysis. The TextBlob tool is used for making analysis which is a predefined sentiment analysis model. TextBlob uses a machine learning algorithm called Naïve Bayes algorithm which is a popular machine learning algorithm that is widely used for text classification tasks including sentiment analysis [1]. It is based on Bayes theorem and assumes independence between the features in a text which makes it computationally efficient and well suited for processing large volumes of text data.

Overall, sentiment analysis is crucial for gaining insights into customer sentiment and preferences. It can offer assistance

businesses make educated choices and move forward client fulfillment by distinguishing zones for change. With the accessibility of progressed machine learning methods and apparatuses, opinion examination has ended up more exact and proficient, making it a profitable device for analyzing expansive datasets of content. It can offer assistance businesses make educated choices and make strides client fulfillment by recognizing ranges for enhancement. With the accessibility of progressed machine learning strategies and instruments, sentiment analysis has gotten to be more precise and productive, making it a profitable apparatus for analyzing huge datasets of content.

A. Experimentation of Sentimental Analysis

For better understanding the domain is being explained in the form of a diagram “Fig .1”.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous sentiment analysis algorithms have been employed in recent years. The article[1] discusses the steps taken in the development of the application, including data

collection, data preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification using the Naive Bayes classifier method. The results of the study show that the application can classify tweets about SAMSAT Kota Malang into positive, negative, and neutral sentiment categories with an accuracy of 83%.

Overall, the article provides insights into the development of a Twitter sentiment analysis application using the Naive Bayes classifier method and highlights the potential applications of this technology in the context of SAMSAT Kota Malang.

The Authors [3] used Naive Bayes algorithm as one of the three supervised machine learning approaches to classify the reviews into positive or negative sentiment categories. They first preprocessed the reviews by removing stop words and applying stemming. Then, they represented each review using a bag-of-words model, where each word in the review is treated as a feature. They used the frequency of each word in the review as a weight for that feature.

Next, they split the dataset into training and testing sets and applied the Naive Bayes algorithm to the training set. The algorithm used the training data to learn the probabilities of each word in the vocabulary given the positive or negative sentiment category.

Overall, the authors found that the Naive Bayes algorithm performed relatively well but was outperformed by the Support Vector Machines algorithm in terms of accuracy and F-measure.

The paper [2] provides an overview of sentiment analysis, its importance, and its applications in various domains, including social media, e-commerce, and healthcare. The authors discuss different approaches to sentiment analysis, including lexicon-based, machine learning, and hybrid approaches that combine both methods. The paper provides a detailed review of various sentiment analysis algorithms, such as Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines, and Maximum Entropy, and compares their performance on different datasets and domains.

The paper provides a comprehensive survey of various applications of sentiment analysis, including opinion mining, brand monitoring, and customer feedback analysis. The authors also discuss the ethical and privacy implications of sentiment analysis, such as protecting user data and avoiding biases. Overall, the paper provides a comprehensive overview of sentiment analysis, its algorithms, applications, and challenges, and is a useful resource for researchers and practitioners working in this field.

M S Neethu and R Rajasree,[4] published in the 2013 Fourth International Conference on Computing, Communications and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), Naive Bayes algorithm was used to classify tweets into positive, negative, or neutral sentiment categories. Here are some key points on how Naive Bayes was used:

The authors preprocessed the tweets by removing stop words, punctuation, and URLs, and then represented them using a bag-of-words model.

They used Naive Bayes algorithm to train a classifier on a labeled dataset of tweets and then used it to predict the sentiment of new, unlabeled tweets. The authors compared the performance of Naive Bayes with other machine learning algorithms, such as Support Vector Machines and Decision Trees, and found that Naive Bayes performed well in terms of accuracy and F-measure. They also experimented with different feature selection techniques, such as mutual information and chi-square, to improve the performance of Naive Bayes. The authors concluded that Naive Bayes is a simple and effective algorithm for sentiment analysis in Twitter, and it can provide reliable predictions with limited training data and noisy text data. Overall, Naive Bayes algorithm was used in this paper to classify tweets into sentiment categories and was found to perform well in comparison to other machine learning algorithms. The authors also experimented with different feature selection techniques to improve its performance.

Vicente García-Díaz et al proposed a new approach called the Hybrid Sentiment Analysis (HSA) method, which combines a Naive Bayes classifier [5] with other machine learning techniques, such as Genetic Algorithms and Particle Swarm Optimization. They used the Naive Bayes classifier to build a baseline sentiment analysis system on a dataset of movie reviews. The authors then used the HSA method to improve the accuracy of the Naive Bayes classifier by selecting the most relevant features for sentiment analysis and optimizing the hyperparameters of the classifier.

The paper [6] used Naive Bayes algorithm to classify reviews into positive and negative sentiment categories. The authors preprocessed the dataset by removing stop words and performing stemming on the reviews. They evaluated the performance of Naive Bayes algorithm in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Naive Bayes outperformed other machine learning algorithms in terms of accuracy and F1-score. The study showed that Naive Bayes can be used effectively for sentiment analysis of reviews.

In conclusion, Naive Bayes has ended up a prevalent choice for wistful investigation assignments due to its straightforwardness, effectiveness, and viability. A few later considers have appeared its victory in different applications, counting but not constrained to e-commerce item audits, tweets, and motion picture audits. Be that as it may, it is fundamental to conduct more investigate to explore the confinements of Naive Bayes and to create more progressed procedures that can handle the complexities of common dialect.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for sentiment analysis of product reviews using TextBlob and Naive Bayes involves several steps. Firstly, a Review model is created with fields such as user,

product, review, and sentiment polarity. The sentiment polarity field is set to the default value of 0.0. Secondly, a function called get sentiment is defined in the Review model, which uses TextBlob to analyze the sentiment polarity of the review and returns the value. Next, a function called sentiment graph is created in the Review model, which uses matplotlib to generate a bar graph based on the average sentiment polarity of reviews for each product. The sentiment graph function saves the graph as an image in a buffer and encodes it as base64 before returning an HTTP response with the graph as an image. Finally, a custom URL is added in the Review model to render the sentiment graph function as a web page. In addition, a function called rateproduct is created to allow users to submit product reviews. The rateproduct function creates a Review object with the user, product, and review data submitted by the user and redirects the user to the home page after submission. This methodology can be applied to any product review dataset to perform sentiment analysis and visualize the results using a bar graph.

IV. BUILD MODEL

For building a reliable and accurate machine learning model for the successful prediction of student performance we follow the following steps using linear regression algorithm

Importing Libraries

```

from textblob import TextBlob
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from django.db.models.functions import ExtractMonth
from django.db.models import Count
  
```

TextBlob is a class used to process textual data. It offers a straightforward API for getting started with typical natural language processing (nlp) activities like part of speech tagging and phrase extraction sentimental analysis classification translation and others.

Matplotlib data visualization library for python.it provides a wide range of tools for creating static animated and interactive visualization in Python it is useful creating line plots scatter plots bar plots and common chart types

Perform Sentimental Analysis

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7955846

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2023, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

```

def get_sentiment(self):
    blob = TextBlob(self.review)
    sentiment_polarity = blob.sentiment.polarity
    return sentiment_polarity
  
```

```

def sentiment_graph(self, request):
    products = product.objects.all()
    data = {}
    for i in products:
        reviews = Review.objects.filter(product=i)
        if reviews.exists():
            sentiment_avg = reviews.aggregate(Avg('sentiment_polarity'))['sentiment_polarity_avg']
            data[i.name] = sentiment_avg or 0
    # generate graph using matplotlib
    fig, ax = plt.subplots()
    fig.set_size_inches(20, 15)
    colors = ['blue' if v > 0 else 'red' if v < 0 else 'green' for v in data.values()]
    ax.bar(data.keys(), data.values(), color=colors)
    ax.set_xlabel('Products')
    ax.set_ylabel('Average Sentiment Polarity')
    ax.set_title('Best Product based on Sentiment Analysis')
    plt.xticks(rotation=45)
    handles = [Patch(facecolor='blue', Label='Positive'),
               Patch(facecolor='red', Label='Negative'),
               Patch(facecolor='green', Label='Neutral')]
    # plt.legend(handles=handles)
    plt.legend(handles=handles, fontsize=20)
    # save graph as image and encode as base64
    buffer = BytesIO()
    plt.savefig(buffer, format='png')
    buffer.seek(0)
    image = base64.b64encode(buffer.getvalue()).decode('utf-8')
  
```

Rate Product

Product Name:

Submit

Database

id	review	product_id	user_id	sentiment_polarity
Filter	Filter	Filter	Filter	Filter
2	bad	5	4	-0.7
3	good	4	4	0.7
4	it is a very good product	1	1	0.91
5	good coin	5	4	0.7
6	it is a good coin	5	4	0.7
7	it is good	1	1	0.7
8	not bad	7	1	0.35

V. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, sentiment analysis with price optimization using TextBlob and Naïve Bayes is a powerful methodology that can help e-commerce sites improve their sales performance and profitability. By analyzing customer sentiment through their reviews and weighting the ratings based on sentiment scores, e-commerce sites can gain a

better understanding of their customers preferences and adjust their pricing strategies accordingly.

TextBlob and Naïve Bayes provide an efficient and accurate way to perform sentiment analysis on large volumes of text data, allowing e-commerce sites to quickly and easily identify patterns in customer feedback. By incorporating sentiment analysis into their pricing algorithms, e-commerce sites can optimize their prices on market demand and customer preferences, resulting in increased revenue and profitability.

VII. REFERENCES

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